

用于形成发展战略业务实体的数字工具（以农工综合体为例）
**DIGITAL TOOLS FOR THE FORMATION OF DEVELOPMENT
STRATEGIES BUSINESS ENTITIES (ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE
AGRO-INDUSTRIAL COMPLEX)**

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如果不提高经济管理决策的质量，俄罗斯经济数字化的成功发展是不可能的。为此，使用经济学、物理学和其他自然科学领域开发的所有大型数据集数字处理工具似乎是合适的。本文证实了经济实体使用数字经济物理工具和统计调节方法提高经济管理决策质量和发展战略形成的可能性。提出了一种基于马科维茨投资组合理论和拒绝趋势线性等可选限制的改进经济实体投资优化方法的变体和其他限制。获得的结果可用于改进估计并提取有关农产工业企业产品生产之间隐藏关系的更多信息，以便在实施其发展战略时做出更有效的管理决策。

关键词：企业实体，发展战略，投资优化方法，马科维茨投资组合理论，经济物理工具。

Abstract. *The successful development of the digitalization of the Russian economy is impossible without improving the quality of economic management decisions. To do this, it seems appropriate to use all the tools for digital processing of large data sets, developed in economics, physics and other natural sciences. This paper substantiates the possibility of improving the quality of economic management decisions and the formation of development strategies by an economic entity using digital econophysical tools and the method of statistical regulation. A variant of improving the methods for optimizing the investments of economic entities based on the theory of investment portfolios of Markowitz and the rejection of optional restrictions such as linearity of trends and other restrictions is proposed. The results obtained can be used to refine estimates and extract*

additional information about the hidden relationship between the production of goods by agro-industrial enterprises in order to make more effective management decisions as part of the implementation of their development strategies.

Keywords: *business entity, development strategy, investment optimization methods, Markowitz investment portfolio theory, econophysical tools.*

1. Introduction

The digitalization of the Russian economy generates large arrays of various data, which, as a rule, contain hidden significant connections that are not obvious to a decision maker who is not armed with modern digital methods. It seems appropriate to use all the tools for digital processing of large data arrays, developed in physics and other natural sciences, to improve the quality of economic management decisions. This paper presents the possibility of digitally improving the quality of choosing an import substitution strategy using computer methods for solving ill-posed physics problems.

2. Literature review

Some works have developed, adapted to the level of linear approximations and visual images, methods for optimizing the investments of business entities based on the theory of investment portfolios by Markowitz [3, 5, 7]. In this paper, we will consider the development of techniques using the simplest variants of the method of statistical regulation [2]. They have been experimentally tested on the example of the implementation of import substitution strategies by large agricultural enterprises and have shown high reliability and efficiency [1]. This makes it possible to improve the methods used in terms of avoiding optional restrictions such as trend linearity, etc.

3. Materials

As experimental data, we will take the indicators of Table 1 from [6], which are indexed by rows m - time, and by columns n - agricultural crops (industries, goods, etc.). The yield of each crop changes every year. This allows us to state that the yield (profitability) is a random variable (see Table 1) superimposed on the trends individual for each crop. Compared with [6], the requirement for the linearity and profitability of agricultural crops in time remains common in the formulation of the problem.

Let's assume that all table data are united by rows by some common trend of arbitrary nature (increasing, descending, quasi-periodic...) while observing the requirement of smoothness. Then it can be argued that the general country and sectoral trends should also affect the dynamics of each of the agricultural crops (industries, goods, etc.), and therefore, linear approximations can be considered as intra-group differences that more accurately distinguish between the effectiveness of investments.

4. Results

A priori, it can be assumed that such a joint rather than line-by-line processing of the entire data array (see Table 1) should allow more accurate assessment of both the differences between agricultural crops and, to an even greater extent, the real pairwise correlations of the temporal dynamics of the yield of various crops.

Formally, this statement corresponds to the notation (1):

$$F = \bar{a} \times \bar{I}_m^T + \bar{b} \times \bar{X}_m^T + \bar{I}_n \times \bar{\gamma}^T + \xi \quad (1),$$

where F – matrix of experimental data based on Table 1;

$\bar{\gamma}$ – the discretization of an arbitrary m -smooth function common to all data;

$\bar{a}$ – vector of constant coefficients of deviations from the general trend;

$\bar{b}$ – vector of coefficients of linear deviations from the general trend;

$\bar{I}_m$ – unit vector ($m \times 1$);

$\bar{I}_n$ – единичный вектор ($n \times 1$);

$\bar{X}_m$ – unit vector ($n \times 1$);

ξ – matrix of residual deviations, which we will a priori consider uncorrelated.

Table 1
Crop yields for 2013-2018

Name of culture	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
Cereals and leguminous crops	22	24,1	23,7	26,2	29,2	25,4
Cereal crops	22,4	24,4	23,9	26,5	29,7	26,2
Wheat	22,3	25	23,9	26,8	31,2	27,2
Winter wheat	29,9	35,1	32	37,6	41,7	35,2
Spring wheat	14,2	14,7	15,5	15,7	18,9	16,8
Rye	18,9	17,7	16,7	20,3	21,7	20
Winter rye	18,9	17,7	16,7	20,3	21,7	20,1
Triticale winter and spring	24,1	26,4	23,1	27,8	29,1	27
Barley	19,2	22,7	21,3	22,1	26,2	21,6
Winter barley	40,3	35,9	40	39,5	41,9	38,8
Spring barley	18,1	21,8	20	20,8	25,2	20,5
Oats	16,4	17,1	16	17,3	19,6	17,3
Rice	49,5	53,6	55,8	53	53,1	57,6
Buckwheat	9,2	9,3	9,5	10,6	10,2	9,5
Millet	11,8	12,3	12,9	15,4	13,4	11,6
Legumes	12,1	14,6	15,9	17,5	20,1	13
Oilseeds	13,3	12,4	12,9	13,9	14,1	14,7
Rape	11,3	12,6	11,2	11	15,8	13,3
Winter rapeseed	16,6	16,8	19,3	18,2	22,7	19,8
Spring rapeseed	9,9	11,2	9,8	10,2	14,5	12,4

Sugar beet	442	370	388	470	442	381
Vegetables	214	219	226	229	241	243
Gourds	105	104	109	119	126	147
Forage crops						
Root crops and sugar beets	273	253	267	255	252	262
Crops for silage (without corn)	97	88	95	99	109	88
Corn for feed	193	159	208	195	185	194
Annual herbs						
for hay	16,7	16,8	16,8	20,2	19,6	18,1
for fodder, haylage, grass meal	71	71	73	76	84	76
Perennial grass						
for hay	16,4	16,3	16,7	18	18,2	17,5
for fodder, haylage, grass meal	1,3	100	104	109	110	102
Cultivated pastures and hayfields						
for hay	16,1	16,3	19,1	16,9	17,4	17,7
for fodder, haylage, grass meal	55,8	61,1	61	55,7	50,6	47,2
Natural hayfields in agricultural organizations						
for hay	9,1	9,3	9,3	10,1	10,3	10,7

With a vector reformulation according to [5], (1) is transformed into a system of linear overdetermined ($m \times n$) equations for $2n + m$ unknowns, represented by a block vector

$$\bar{\varphi} = [\bar{a}; \bar{b}; \bar{\gamma}] \quad (2)$$

Omitting the transformations that are optional for this article, the statistical regularized solution (1) taking into account (2) has the form

$$\bar{\varphi}_\lambda = (K^T \times K + \lambda \times \Omega_2)^{-1} \times K^T \times \bar{f} \quad (3),$$

where K is a block matrix of the form:

$m \times E_n$	$\langle \bar{X} \rangle \times E_n$	$\bar{I}_n \times \bar{I}_m^T$
$\langle \bar{X} \rangle \times E_n$	$((\bar{X}^T \times \bar{X})) \times E_n$	$\bar{I}_n \times \bar{X}^T$
$\bar{I}_m \times \bar{I}_n^T$	$\bar{X} \times \bar{I}_n^T$	$n \times E_m$

$$= K \quad (4)$$

$\bar{f}$ – block vector of the form:

$$[\bar{f}_1; \bar{f}_2; \bar{f}_3] = \bar{f} \quad (5)$$

$$\text{where } \bar{f}_1 = F \times \bar{I}_m \quad (6)$$

$$\bar{f}_2 = F \times \bar{X}_m \quad (7)$$

$$\bar{f}_3 = F^T \times \bar{I}_n \quad (8)$$

E - unity Diagonal Matrix,

$$\langle \bar{X} \rangle = (\bar{X}_m^T \times \bar{I}_m) \quad (9)$$

Ω_2 – Tikhonov-type block stabilizer [5] in the simplest case using second-order smoothness on $\bar{a}$ и $\bar{b}$.

λ – stabilizing parameter, in the simplest version, calculated in 1 step according to the formula

$$\lambda = \frac{S_p(K \times \Omega_2^{-1} \times K^T \times A)}{(\bar{f}^T \times A \times \bar{f}) - S_p(V_\xi \times A)} \quad (10),$$

where A – an arbitrary matrix, which, in particular, can be E, Ω_2 etc.;

V_ξ – a covariance matrix of random deviations from trends ξ , which are a priori assumed to be independent and normal with a given dispersion equation.

Although from general considerations, the joint processing of a type 1 table by (1-10) should give more accurate and stable estimates of the elements $\bar{a}$ and $\bar{b}$, чем построчная обработка коротких временных рядов по m-индексу. Поэтому прежде чем рекомендовать ее к практическому использованию целесообразно проверить ее на модельных экспериментах.

Below are selected results of a series of such cyclic experiments, where $\bar{I}_n$ are chosen as $\bar{a}_0, \bar{b}_0 = 0,05 \times \bar{X}_n$, as b , and $\bar{V}_0$ is a quadratic curve of the form $(0,01 \div 0,1) (\bar{X}_m \otimes \bar{X}_m)$, where $\otimes$ is the symbol of element-wise multiplication, ξ random errors with standard deviation from 0.01 to 0.2.

According to the results of model experiments, the deviations of the reconstructed values $\bar{A}_\lambda, \bar{B}_\lambda, \bar{\gamma}_\lambda$ from the true values were compared with the deviations $\bar{A}_0, \bar{B}_0$ from $\bar{A}_R, \bar{B}_R$, calculated line by line using the standard multiple correlation method.

The results were compared according to the estimates of standard deviations:

$$SA_\lambda = ((\bar{A}_\lambda - \bar{A}_0)^T \times (\bar{A}_\lambda - \bar{A}_0))^{1/2}; \quad SB_\lambda = ((\bar{B}_\lambda - \bar{B}_0)^T \times (\bar{B}_\lambda - \bar{B}_0))^{1/2} \quad (11)$$

$$SA_\lambda = ((\bar{A}_\lambda - \bar{A}_0)^T \times (\bar{A}_\lambda - \bar{A}_0))^{1/2}; \quad SB_\lambda = ((\bar{B}_\lambda - \bar{B}_0)^T \times (\bar{B}_\lambda - \bar{B}_0))^{1/2} \quad (12)$$

5. Discussion

The first estimates showed the stability of the regularized algorithms for all realistic error levels and a two-threefold decrease in the residual SA_λ, SB_λ compared to line-by-line processing SA_0, SB_0 . This allows us to recommend the methodology for processing real multi-commodity (diversified) data tables.

In addition, digital experiments show the possibility of visualizing the choice of the most profitable crop, taking into account the possible risk in the simplest version of the linear objective combined function $\bar{U}$ of the form

$$\bar{U} = z \times \bar{P}(m+1) - (1-z) \times \bar{\delta}(m+1) \quad (13)$$

where z – parameter $(0 \div 1)$;

$\bar{P}(m+1)$ – resulting projected returns in the $(m+1)$ year;

$\bar{\delta}(m+1)$ – predictive estimates of standard deviations of crop yields for the $(m+1)$ year.

In the model example, crops are ranked by return from 0 to 30, and risks grow in antiphase with return.

The typical result presented in Figure 1 illustrates the visual possibilities of the methodology and the feasibility of improving the objective function (13) taking into account modern ideas about the asymmetry of income and losses [4].

The result presented in Figure 2 illustrates the difference made in the calculation of industry-wide trends by conventional averaging and smoothing by (3) under conditions of errors comparable to the annual increase in yield.

In general, theoretical estimates and model tests allow us to begin experimental testing of the method of statistical regularized assessment of general trends in profitability and the most efficient industries in practice.

6. Conclusion

Figure 1. Combined return of different crops with different levels of risk

Figure 2. Smoothed by (3) and averaged in the usual way (according to the OLS) integral return with an error level comparable to the increase in return.

Thus, in this article, studies were carried out and results were obtained on closed digital model experiments with closed data close to practically recorded ones. When determining a ranked list of import-substituting crops, it was shown

that it is possible to refine estimates and extract additional information about the hidden relationship of produced goods (crops) in order to make more effective management decisions.

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